

Evolution of the average obscured star formation and AGNs in a protocluster through infrared all-sky surveys

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Protoclusters

Protoclusters

Many protoclusters have been found & studied in detail but ...

Image of Spiderweb protocluster © ESO/M. Kornmesser

Cosmic web in SSA22 protocluster (Umehata+2019)

SPT2349-56 (Miller+2018)

$z=7.88$ protocluster (Morishita+2023)

Protoclusters

What are the critical problems of putting together observational results into one scenario?

- The selection bias of protoclusters has not yet been understood well.
- It is hard to measure the halo masses of protoclusters robustly. We do not know how special (or not special) our target protoclusters are ...
- Data quality is not uniform. Especially, observations at X-ray and FIR, which are necessary to characterize AGN and SFR, are lacking.

Protoclusters and dusty star-forming galaxies

SMGs in a protocluster at $z=3.1$ Tamura+2009

Many dusty star-forming galaxies, hardly observed in the optical, are likely in protoclusters.

Dusty protocluster at $z=4$ Miller+2018

Protoclusters and AGNs

- There is a BH mass and bulge mass relation, and AGNs are thought to play key roles in galaxy quenching in simulations.
- When BH vs. bulge mass relation was formed? Does AGN feedback truly work effectively?
- However, the observations of AGNs in protoclusters are quite limited.
- SMBHs continuously evolve after star formation quenching in massive halos? (Zhang+2022)

AGNs along SSA22 large scale structure.

Kubo+2022

TRINITY, a flexible empirical model of constraining dark matter haloes, galaxy, and SMBH connection statistically (Zhang+2022)

What do we need: Statistical study of (star formation and AGNs in) protoclusters

What is needed?

- What are the typical protoclusters? → Unbiased and wide survey
- Statistical studies of dusty star formation and AGNs are also needed.
- Needless to say, detailed studies of protoclusters are important, but to understand how the observed phenomena drive the evolution of protoclusters better, we need to know the global history of protoclusters.

This work

- I. Average infrared properties of protoclusters at $z \sim 4$ selected with the Subaru Hyper Suprime-Cam (HSC) (Kubo+2019)
- II. Environments of luminous radio-loud AGNs in the IR (Kubo+ in prep)

I. Average infrared properties of HSC protoclusters at $z \sim 4$

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Sample selection

HSC-SSP survey: Uniform, deep, and multi-band (grizy, $I \sim 26$ mag, ~ 1000 deg² in WIDE Layer) imaging survey using Hyper Suprime-Cam (HSC) on Subaru Telescope

I. Average infrared properties of HSC protoclusters at $z \sim 4$

Sample selection

189 candidate protoclusters at $z \sim 4$ (expected to evolve into $M_H > 10^{14} M_{\text{sun}}$ clusters) were selected over 121 deg² based on the overdense regions of g-dropout Lyman Break Galaxies (Toshikawa+2018).

First systematic large survey of protoclusters

I. Average infrared properties of HSC protoclusters at $z \sim 4$

Method

To constrain the total SFRs of protoclusters, dust emission in the IR should be constrained. However it is hard to perform observations in the FIR to sub-mm for many protoclusters...

Large ($N \geq 100$) protocluster catalog + WISE ~ Planck : Average of the total infrared emission and SED of a protocluster

I. Average infrared properties of HSC protoclusters at $z \sim 4$

Method

- Stacking analysis is performed for 189 protoclusters selected from the HSC-SSP survey.
- WISE, IRAS, AKARI, Planck, & Herschel SPIRE (half of the sample is in H-ATLAS. PACS is not useful because of over-sky subtraction) are useful.
- Stacking analysis is performed after subtracting the sky and smoothing the PSF to Planck (For simplicity. But it results in poor S/N for WISE...).
- Fluxes and errors are the median and standard deviation of boot-strap resampling.

I. Average infrared properties of HSC protoclusters at $z \sim 4$

Results

- Significant detections at WISE W3, IRAS, AKARI, Planck, and SPIRE.
- Extended emission (8 arcmin diameter) at Herschel SPIRE

I. Average infrared properties of HSC protoclusters at $z \sim 4$

Discussion: significant hidden star formation on average

Brighter half: Similar stacking analysis for sub-sample based on tentative detections on Planck

Black points: Stacking analysis of field g-dropout galaxies using WISE and Herschel.

I. Average infrared properties of HSC protoclusters at $z \sim 4$

Discussion: origin of the IR emission

SED: Fitted by young hot starburst ($T_d=70$ K) or SFG+AGN models.

SFR vs. redshift: At least, the average of total LIR of a protocluster continuously evolve toward $z \sim 4$ (Except for our sample, no statistical study was available)

I. Average infrared properties of HSC protoclusters at $z \sim 4$

What to do next: $z < 3$ environments using radio-loud AGNs

Protoclusters at cosmic noon ($z=2\sim 3$) cannot be selected by the HSC-SSP WIDE, only by an optical survey.

At this point, luminous radio-loud AGNs, which are believed to be hosted by massive ($>10^{13.5}$ Msun) halos, can be used as the signposts of protoclusters (e.g., CARLA survey, Spiderweb).

A similar infrared stacking analysis is performed for radio-loud AGNs (Kubo+in prep)

II. Environments of luminous radio-loud AGNs in the IR.

II. Environments of luminous radio-loud AGNs in the IR

Sample selection and method

Targets: luminous radio-loud AGNs at $1 < z < 3$

- Radio sources are taken from the NVSS survey ($L_{1.4 \text{ GHz}} \geq 10^{27} \text{ erg/s}$).
- Spectroscopic redshifts are available from SDSS or literature
- 40 to 304 objects / $\Delta z = 0.5$ at $0.75 < z < 3.25$.

Infrared stacking analysis

- Almost the same as Kubo+2019
- But PSF matching is not performed (Then foreground objects on WISE images are better subtracted).
- The fluxes at the outer region can be missed by WISE stacking (It does not affect SFR measurement relying on Planck. But it can underestimate M^* and AGN emission)

II. Environments of luminous radio-loud AGNs in the IR

Detection at WISE and Planck (no detection at IRAS/AKARI).

II. Environments of luminous radio-loud AGNs in the IR

Results

Significantly extended at WISE compared to the stacks of random points (= **emission does not come solely from radio-loud AGNs**)

Black: Stacking analysis of radio-loud AGNs, Blue: PSF,

Red: Stacking analysis for random points with magnitude distribution similar to radio-loud AGNs in this study (no detection = random sky)

II. Environments of luminous radio-loud AGNs in the IR

Results

Is the emission from the central radio-loud AGNs or the vicinities?

- Planck: larger emission than the fluxes expected for a radio-loud AGN.
- WISE: Extended emission. The stacked fluxes are much larger than those measured on individual images of radio-loud AGNs.

II. Environments of luminous radio-loud AGNs in the IR

Results

- The observed SEDs are fitted with composites of SFG templates (empirical model, Danielson+17) and AGN templates.
- SFR is calculated from the best-fit SFG model.
- BHAR is calculated by scaling the bolometric luminosities of the best-fit AGN model.

Hardly explained by SFG models.

II. Environments of luminous radio-loud AGNs in the IR

Discussion: evolution of SFR and BH accretion rate (BHAR)

- Both SFR and BHAR evolve toward high redshift. Large values than the TNG300 halos with $13.5 < \log M_H / M_{\text{sun}} < 14$ (expected mass of radio-loud AGN from clustering analysis in literature) at each redshift.
- Maybe there is a large uncertainty in radio-loud AGN halo mass. But at $z \sim 3$, even though it is compared to more massive halos in TNG300 at that epoch, the total SFR is higher...there should also be SFR underestimation.

II. Environments of luminous radio-loud AGNs in the IR

Discussion: difference in SFH and BH growth history

- Compared to SFR, BHAR evolution is modest.
- Similar to Zhang+2022, BHs continuously grow after the star formation in massive clusters has been quenched. Such AGNs maintain the star formation quenching?

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Conclusion and future prospects for Euclid

- The average of the total mid to far-infrared emission of protoclusters is successfully shown using the large protocluster catalog and infrared archive.
- There are significant dusty star formation and AGNs **on average** in a protocluster.
- The SFR and BHAR of radio-loud AGN environments increase with redshift. **There is a possible difference between the star formation and BH growth histories in massive halos like protoclusters.**
- Euclid will provide unbiased catalogs of clusters/protoclusters at $z < 3$: It will allow us to track the SFR and BH evolution histories for the similar descendant mass system.
- This method can also be applied to $z \sim 6$ systems (Kubo+in prep).